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Assessment of seasonal and spatial water quality variation in a

3

cascading lake system in Chennai, India

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Highlights

- The lake water quality is better in downstream lakes than in upstream lakes and is better after monsoon season.
- The lake water quality is negatively impacted by crops, woodland and urban area but is positively impacted by grass land.
- More attention should be paid to protecting the water quality from the local authorities, decision-makers, and the residents.

Graphic abstract

21 **Abstract**

22 Water quality and scarcity are among the most severe problems humans have been facing in
23 the last decades. India, as a fast-developing country, is not an exception. The surface water
24 quality has deteriorated due to anthropogenic activities. Another factor which impacts the water
25 quality is the heavy rainfall during monsoon season. To maintain the quality and the
26 sustainability of water resources, there is the need to study how human activities impact water
27 quality. We hypothesized that the water quality can be impacted by the spatial land use types
28 and by the seasonality. In the present study, seasonal and spatial water quality regarding
29 physical, chemical, and biological parameters from a lake cascading system was assessed
30 monthly from July to December 2019. Land use/cover data was produced by Impact
31 Observatory, Microsoft, and Esri based on the 10-meter Sentinel-2 images. Redundancy
32 analysis was applied to investigate the relationship between land use/cover data and water
33 quality in the riparian of 500 and 1000 m to the lakes. Our results showed clear temporal and
34 spatial variation of water quality in 2019, with better water quality in rainy season (Oct.-Dec.)
35 and downstream lakes while relatively worse water quality was recorded in dry season (Jul.-
36 Sep.) and upstream lakes. The water quality variation was explained 27.8% and 42.7% by the
37 land use types within 500 m and 1000 m buffer widths, respectively. The outlet of the
38 catchment showed exceptional results due to the impact of a dumpsite. Our findings indicate
39 that the water quality is highly impacted by human-induced land use/cover. The land use/cover
40 types, such as crops, woodland and urban area, show negative impacts and relate to the high
41 level of nutrient concentrations. In opposite, grass land shows positive effects and leads to
42 better water quality. Our study confirms that the lake water quality is distinguished in both
43 spatial and seasonal aspects. Monsoon season improves the water quality.

44 **1. Introduction**

45 Water quality and scarcity are among the most severe problems humans have been facing in
46 the whole world. India is not an exception to this worldwide issue, and it has been suffering
47 from severe water scarcity and pollution for decades. The country has 16% of total population
48 of the world but only 4% of world's total water resources (Dutta, 2019). Surface and ground
49 water are the main sources of freshwater supply. Currently, 600 million Indians face high to
50 extreme water stress and about two hundred thousand people die every year due to inadequate
51 access to safe water (Aayog, 2018). Rapid population growth, urbanization, pollution,
52 deforestation, and climate change, among others, are leading India to a water related
53 vulnerability that will influence the society in an unfavorable manner (Tripathy and Raha,
54 2019). According to Aayog's Composite Water Management Index report, eleven of India's
55 twenty largest cities face an 'extreme risk' of water stress and seven are in 'high risk' (Aayog,
56 2018). Almost every single city and village in the country has lost its wetlands, water bodies
57 and even rivers to meet the needs of rising population (Upadhyay, 2019). Furthermore, India
58 and other developing countries suffer from absence of data, inaccessibility, or low reliability,
59 and therefore, it is difficult to diagnose the actual status of water bodies (Aartsen et al., 2018).

60 Chennai is the fourth major metropolitan area in India, with a population over 8 million (Aithal
61 and Ramachandra, 2016) and is one of the eleven cities facing an 'extreme risk' of water stress.
62 It had nearly about 150 small and big water bodies and wetlands in and around the city but only
63 27 left in 2009 (Chandramohan and Bharati, 2009). Pallikaranai marshland, for instance, is the
64 largest marshland in the region (Jayaprakash et al., 2010), and one of the last remaining natural
65 wetlands in south India (Mariappan, 2011). However, the marshland has shrunken from about
66 5500 hectares in the year 1965 to about 600 hectares currently (Surya, 2016), with a high loss
67 of biodiversity. The marshland holds nowadays one of the two biggest dumpsites of Chennai,
68 which receives about 2100 tons of waste generated by Chennai city every day (Jayaprakash et

69 al., 2010). Furthermore, agricultural fields surrounding the lakes have been replaced by other
70 land use types.

71 It has been reported that the different combination of landscapes in the riparian have different
72 effects on water quality (Li et al., 2018), particularly the urban use has a huge impact, mostly
73 negative. Owing to the development of GIS technology, remote sensing data (Schneider et al.,
74 2010; Sexton et al., 2013; Stokes and Seto, 2019) could produce the information of urban
75 expansion dynamics, which is fundamental for analyzing the land use patterns and interpreting
76 the human impacts on water quality (Fernandes et al., 2021; Paiva et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2020;
77 Yang et al., 2022). Besides the remote sensing data, the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer
78 Suite (VIIRS) Night-time Light (VNL) could also be used to produce urban expansion maps
79 (Wang et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2022, 2021) to investigate influence of
80 human activities. Furthermore, the VIIRS VNL has been used to investigate biodiversity (Hu
81 et al., 2018) and water sustainability research (Mukherjee et al., 2019). In addition to the land
82 use types, the main influencing factors can be various in different buffer lengths (Li et al.,
83 2018). To our knowledge, there is rare research about the land use the its impact on water
84 quality in Chennai lakes.

85 In addition, the surface water quality can show obvious seasonal variability (Zhang et al., 2021).
86 Rainfall was reported to have inconsistent effects on the nutrient concentration in water bodies,
87 which could lead to either an increase or decrease of the concentrations (Kaushal et al., 2008).
88 On the one hand, the rainfall can increase the concentrations by rushing the pollutants from the
89 basin into the water bodies (Risch et al., 2018). On the other hand, the rainfall can cause dilution
90 effects which decline the concentrations (Allafta and Opp, 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). However,
91 the monsoon effects on the water quality of Chennai urban water bodies are not fully explored
92 yet.

93 To address this research issue, we have assessed the water quality of the lakes in a cascading
94 system in Pallikaranai catchment in Chennai City from July to December 2019. We aimed 1)
95 to investigate the influence of the monsoon season on water quality, 2) to quantify the spatial
96 variability of water quality in the cascading system, 3) to explore the relationship between
97 surface water quality and the surrounding land use patterns, and 4) to provide some suggestions
98 for the future management.

99 **2. Material and Methods**

100 **2.1. Study area**

101 The ~50-km² Pallikaranai catchment (Figure 1), located appr. 20 km south of Chennai city,
 102 consists of seven lakes and a marshland. Annual summer temperature ranges between 35° and
 103 42°, while annual winter temperature ranges 25° - 34° (Azeez et al., 2007). The climate is
 104 subdivided in four seasons: post-monsoon (January-March), summer (April-June), pre-
 105 monsoon (July-September) and monsoon (October-December; Raveen et al., 2008).
 106 Chitlapakkam, Selaiyur and Rajakilpakkam are the upstream lakes, which flow into
 107 Sembakkam Lake. The outflow of it is connected to Nanmangalam Lake. Other downstream
 108 lakes are Keelkatalai, Narayanapuram and the outlet of the catchment, Okkiyam Maduvu. By
 109 Okkiyam Maduvu, the Pallikaranai marshland is connected with the Bay of Bengal through the
 110 Buckingham Canal. These lakes, locally called tanks, are artificial and were dug for irrigation
 111 purposes decades ago by the inhabitants of Chennai, when agriculture was the predominant
 112 land use in the area.

113
 114 Figure 1 Allocation of the lakes and sampling sites' distribution with coordinates in Pallikaranai
 115 catchment, Chennai, India.

116 The precipitation data (Fig. S1) from the closest weather station (source: Chennai Metro Water
117 Supply and Sewage Board) to our study area indicated that it was extremely dry in 2019 and
118 there was barely rain in the first half of the year (Ray Biswas et al., 2022). One of the lakes in
119 the cascading system, Keelkatalai, was even totally dried out (Fig. S2 A). For the second half
120 of the year, the monthly sum of the precipitation was 193.8, 172.2, 245.3, 310.3, 207.4, 168.5
121 mm from July to December, respectively. The total precipitation volume was 1297.5 mm. The
122 lakes were by then over-flooded (e.g., Fig. S2 B, Keelkatalai Lake).

123 **2.2. In-situ parameters, sampling and lab analysis**

124 From July to December 2019, monthly sampling campaigns were conducted. On site, we
125 measured pH, water temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO) and electrical conductivity (EC)
126 values with a Portable Multi-Parameter Meter HQ40d (Hach) at 20-30 cm depth. The portable
127 device was calibrated in situ with the standards provided by the manufacturer. We took 1 Liter
128 water samples from each outlet of the seven lakes and from the outlet of the marshland,
129 following procedures described in standards ISO 5667-1:2006 (sampling) and ISO 5667-
130 3:2012 (preservation). Due to the limited access to all outlets of the lakes, we sampled from
131 the point closest to the outlets. Data for Keelkatalai Lake from July to September is missing
132 because the lake was completely dry because of the extreme drought. For Rajakilpakkam Lake,
133 data is missing in December due to the floods of the surroundings of the Lake.

134 Samples were placed in a portable refrigerator (4°C) in the dark and transported within 8 hours
135 to the laboratories of the Department of Civil Engineering of the Indian Institute of Technology
136 Madras, where chemical analyses were undertaken. The water samples were then analyzed
137 following several methods of APHA (APHA, 2012): turbidity (turb), 2130 B, total dissolved
138 solids (TDS), 2540 C, total suspended solids (TSS), 2540 D, chemical oxygen demand (COD),
139 5210 C, ammoniacal nitrogen (NH₄-N), 4500-NH₃ F, total phosphorus (TP), 4500-P D,

140 dissolved phosphorus (DP), 4500-P D, chloride (Cl⁻), 4500-Cl B, sulfate (SO₄²⁻), 4500-SO₄²⁻ E
141 and chlorophyll *a* (chl-*a*), 10200-H.

142 **2.3.Remote sensing data**

143 The topographical data (Figure 2, A), including elevation and slope was derived from the 30
144 m SRTM Digital Elevation Database from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration
145 of USA (NASA, <https://www.nasa.gov/>). The VIIRS VNL data with 15 arc second (~500m at
146 the Equator) was required from the Earth Observation Group, Payne Institute for Public Policy,
147 Colorado School of Mines (Elvidge et al., 2017; 2021). The resolution of VNL were 500 m
148 and 1000 m. The land use/cover classification (Figure 2, B) in the 2019 was produced by
149 Impact Observatory, Microsoft, and Esri based on the 10 m Sentinel-2 images
150 (<https://livingatlas.arcgis.com/landcover/>). The land use was categorized into six types,
151 including trees/woodland, flooded vegetation, crops, built area, bare ground, and rangeland
152 (Karra et al., 2021). In the Pallikaranai catchment, land uses distribution was water 4.9%, trees
153 0.7%, flood vegetation 2.6%, crops 4.8%, buit area 80.4%, bar ground 0.3%, and rangeland
154 6.2%. The land use changes were analyzed in different buffer widths of 50, 100, 500, and 1000
155 m (Figure 2, C) from the lakes. Then redundancy analysis (RDA) was used to determine what
156 land use types influenced the water quality in R (R Core Team, 2020).

157

158 Figure 2 The topographical information (A), land use/cover types (B) of Pallikaranai catchment and the
 159 example of buffer lengths (C).

160 **3. Results**

161 **3.1. Spatio-temporal variation of water quality**

162 Fig. S 3 summarizes the correlation between the water quality parameters. Some parameters,
163 for instance, TDS and EC (coefficient: 0.964), Cl and EC (0.912), TP and DP (0.898) show
164 significant linear correlation, others don't show obvious collinearity. The diagonal shows the
165 distribution (in density) of each variable; above the diagonal shows the correlation coefficients
166 between each pair of the parameters plus the level of significance; below the diagonal shows
167 the bivariate scatter plots.

168 Parameters show clear seasonal variation (Figure 3). Most of the parameters' concentration
169 decreased and reached the lowest values in December. Particularly, DO, EC, TDS and chl-*a*
170 concentration showed obvious decrease from July to December. Water temperature decreased
171 from July to September, reached highest temperature in October and then dropped again till
172 December. pH values varied but dropped to around 8.0 in December. Mean NH₃-N
173 concentration was low (around 5 mg/L) from July to September, but increased in October and
174 decreased again till December, with extreme high values at Okiyam Maduvu. TP and DP
175 increased from July to September and then decreased till December. With small fluctuations,
176 other parameters like turbidity, COD, TSS, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻ also showed a clear decreasing trend.

177 The variation of parameters' average values in pre-monsoon (dry) and monsoon (rainy) seasons
178 is summarized (Figure 4). Most of the parameters show a similar trend of increase in monsoon
179 season and decrease in the pre-monsoon season. Mean values of the EC, COD, TP, DP, chl-*a*,
180 TDS, SO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻ in rainy season were lower than the ones in the dry season. However, NH₃-
181 N was an exception with higher values in rainy season and lower values in dry season. Other
182 parameters including temperature, pH, DO, Turb, and TSS show better results in rainy season

183 than dry season in all the lakes except at Okiyam Maduvu. The spatial variation along the flow
184 direction of the lake cascading system is relatively clear. The three head water lakes had higher
185 values of the parameters, the values dropped in downstream lakes; however, the values at the
186 outlet Okiyam Maduvu were extremely high. Mean values of the six-month sampling show
187 various trends for the 15 parameters. Water temperature varied slightly among all the sampling
188 sites. pH and DO don't show clear variation between dry and rainy seasons. Concentration of
189 EC, Turb, COD, TDS, TSS, and Cl^- demonstrates similar trends, with a decrease from upstream
190 until Lake Keelkatalai followed by an increase until Okiyam Maduvu. The average of these
191 parameters was better in rainy season than in dry season. The trend of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, TP and DP was
192 decreasing with a sudden increase at Okiyam Maduvu, while the average was better in dry
193 season than in rainy season. Chl-*a* concentration decreased along the flow direction, while
194 SO_4^{2-} lacked a clear changing trend, but neither of them show clear trend in comparison of rainy
195 and dry seasons.

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Figure 3 Seasonal variation of the parameters measured in Pallikaranai catchment from July to December 2019. Boxplot shows the average values of all the lakes sampled in the same month (units are in the brackets). Abbreviations: DO = dissolved oxygen, EC = electrical conductivity, COD = chemical oxygen demand, NH₃-N = ammoniacal-nitrogen, DP = dissolved phosphate, TP = total phosphate, Chl-a = chlorophyll *a*, TDS = total dissolved solids, TSS = total suspended solids.

202
 203 Figure 4 Parameters' spatial variation along lake flow direction of Pallikaranai catchment from July to
 204 December 2019, with the mean value of pre-monsoon (dry) season (in circles), and the mean value of
 205 monsoon (rainy) season (in diamonds). Abbreviations: DO = dissolved oxygen, EC = electrical
 206 conductivity, COD = chemical oxygen demand, NH₃-N = ammoniacal-nitrogen, DP = dissolved
 207 phosphate, TP = total phosphate, Chl-a = chlorophyll *a*, TDS = total dissolved solids, TSS = total
 208 suspended solids. Lake names of x-axis from left to right: Chitlapakkam, Selaiyur, Rajakilpakkam,
 209 Sembakkam, Nanmangalam, Keelkatalai, Narayanapuram, and the outlet of the catchment, Okkiyam
 210 Maduvu.

211 **3.2. Water quality-land use relationship**

212 Built area was the dominant land use/cover in the Pallikaranai catchment with a proportion of

213 appr. 80%. It was also the dominant land use/cover for all buffer widths from the lakes (Figure
 214 5) although its percentage decreased when greater buffer was considered. The second and third
 215 dominant land use/cover types were crops and rangeland (grass). As an exception,
 216 Narayanapuram Lake showed 100% built area even in the 1000 m buffer zone.

217 The water quality variation was explained 27.8% and 42.7% by the land use types within 500
 218 m and 1000 m buffer widths, respectively. The significant variables, which were relevant with
 219 the water quality variation, were recognized by the RDA. With the buffer width of 500m, the
 220 first axis explained around 15% of the variation (Figure 6 (A)). The crops and wood land use
 221 had a positive relationship with NH₃-H. The night light data had a positive relationship with
 222 TP and TSS while land use of grass and bare land had a negative relationship with TP. The
 223 flooded vegetation has a positive relationship with chl-*a*. Situation in the 1000m buffer width
 224 was similar, with the first axis explained by 17% (Figure 6 (B)). The land use of wood land
 225 and crops had a positive relationship with both NH₃-H and TP, whereas the grass and bare land
 226 showed negative relationships. However, built area had a negative relationship with NH₃-N
 227 and TP. Flooded vegetation showed a negative relationship with chl-*a* rather than positive.

228
 229 Figure 5 Land use/cover composition (in percentage) in different buffer widths of 50, 100, 500, and
 230 1000 m. Lake names of x-axis from left to right: Chitlapakkam, Selaiyur, Rajakilpakkam, Sembakkam,
 231 Nanmangalam, Keelkatalai, Narayanapuram, and the outlet of the catchment, Okkiyam Maduvu.

233 Figure 6 Reduntancy analysis of topographical and land use/cover effects on water quality within 500
 234 m (A) and 1000 m (B) buffer widths. Abbreviations: DO = dissolved oxygen, EC = electrical
 235 conductivity, Turb = turbidity, COD = chemical oxygen demand, NH3-N = ammoniacal-nitrogen, TP
 236 = total phosphorous, Chl-a = chlorophyll *a* ($\mu\text{g/L}$), TDS = total dissolved solids (mg/L), TSS = total
 237 suspended solids (mg/L), SO4 = sulphate (mg/L), Cl = chloride (mg/L).

238 **4. Discussion**

239 The field visits and the lab analyses have shown that the lakes are in a polluted situation.
240 Human activities affect the water quality deeply. Considering the parameters we measured,
241 downstream lakes show better water quality than the upstream ones, but the outlet sampling
242 point Okkiyam Maduvu is an exception. From a temporal point of view, most water quality
243 parameters in rainy season are better than dry season but $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ is an exception that its values
244 are lower in dry season.

245 Spatially, the water quality of downstream lakes is better than the upstream ones. This could
246 be caused by the dominant built area of the land use types (Figure 5). The first three upstream
247 lakes Chitlapakkam, Selaiyur, Rajakilpakkam are surrounded by almost only built area, while
248 the downstream lakes have more grass and crops land in the surroundings. Upstream lakes
249 showed higher levels of DO, turbidity, phosphate, COD and chl-*a*. The high COD value
250 indicates a heavy organic pollution, which can be explained by the discharge of municipal
251 sewage, domestic sewage, and urban wash off into the water bodies in the upstream area (Devi
252 et al., 2020; Kumar and Tortajada, 2020). Compared to the higher concentration of turbidity,
253 phosphate, TSS, COD from Okkiyam Maduvu, chl-*a* concentration is very low. Low
254 concentration of chl-*a* represents a low phytoplanktonic biomass, which could be caused by
255 other toxic materials from the nearby dumpsite preventing its growth. Furthermore, the increase
256 of TSS may explain it since it reduces light penetration into the water and affect the growth of
257 plankton and fish. However, Okkiyam Maduvu shows much higher COD, $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ and
258 phosphorus than the other downstream lakes, indicating a high eutrophic state. The low water
259 quality may be caused by the improper discharging sewage and trash into the rivers and lakes,
260 which have been widely found as the reason of the water degradation in other water bodies
261 (Alobaidy et al., 2010; Khorramabadi Shams et al., 2014; Mirzaei et al., 2016). Additionally,

262 the leaking effect of the dumpsite inside the marshland may play a big role on affecting the
263 water quality.

264 From our results, the monsoon season increases the water quality. The range of some physico-
265 chemical parameters like pH, EC, DO, TDS, Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} , is similar to some other Chennai
266 lakes (Sunantha and Vasudevan, 2016a). The high concentrations of TDS (~1000 mg/L), Cl^-
267 (~ 50-250 mg/L) and SO_4^{2-} (~ 200-600 mg/L) indicate the inflow from industrial effluent,
268 sewage, or other human activities. Compared to the lakes studied here, the Pulicat Lake in
269 Northern Chennai has a lower concentration of DO (3.1 to 4.8 mg/L) and ortho-phosphate (0.1
270 to 0.9 mg/L) in monsoon season, while the maximum phosphate was recorded in monsoon
271 period due to the additional supply from riverine input and rainfall run-off (Kannan and
272 Krishnamoorthy, 2006). Additionally, higher DO concentration is also found in Oct.-Dec. from
273 Selaiyur, Chitlapakam and Sembakkam lakes than in pre-monsoon season (Raveen et al. 2008),
274 which is possibly caused by the rainfall runoff. The surface runoff of precipitation contributes
275 much to the nutrient concentrations in our study as well. As mentioned before, it was an
276 extreme dry year in Chennai in 2019, the rainfall started in pre-monsoon season. After the
277 extreme dry period, the first rainfalls cause the flushing of all the pollutants from the lake banks
278 and rivers into the lakes. The rainfall in monsoon season increases the lake water level, in
279 which case the pollutants in the lakes are strongly diluted. This might explain why the water
280 quality is better in the monsoon season. This hypothesis is consistent with the decrease of EC,
281 TDS and chloride during the monsoon season. Besides the physico-chemical parameters, as a
282 good indicator of the phytoplanktonic biomass (Parinet et al., 2004), the average concentration
283 of chl-*a*'s decreased along the study time period. Despite the decreasing trend, chl-*a*
284 concentration was still high, indicating a eutrophication state most of the study period (Li et
285 al., 2022; Sutula et al., 2017). This is consistent with the trophic state based on the phosphate
286 and $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ concentrations, since they are co-related (Li et al., 2020). Furthermore, according

287 to Indian Drinking Water Standard (<0.5 mg/L; INDIAN BIS), the $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ values indicate the
288 water quality is not suitable for using as water sources for human and domestic consumption
289 including drinking purpose without treatment. Due to the positive relationship between $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$
290 and crops and wood land, the sources of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ could be the runoff from the land which has
291 been applied fertilizers (Ulén et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2021). Other pollutant
292 sources of surface water include, pesticides, farm manures, septic tank effluent, and animal
293 wastes (Brindha et al., 2010; Sharma and Kansal, 2011; Carmen and Daniela, 2012; Odukkathil
294 and Vasudevan, 2013; Kumar et al., 2017). In addition, the lakes are being polluted by disposal
295 of industrial waste (Sunantha and Vasudevan, 2016b) including heavy metals (Usharani and
296 Vasudevan, 2016). Apart from the domestic waste and sewage, persistent organic pollutants,
297 perfluorinated compounds that could cause severe human health problems, have been also
298 reported being detected in the surface water of Chennai (Sunantha and Vasudevan, 2016b). In
299 addition, the marshland is contaminated with heavy metals (Jayaprakash et al., 2010). The lakes
300 are suffering from encroachment, solid waste disposal, and untreated wastewater discharges,
301 resulting in siltation, sludge deposition and lake eutrophication.

302 The water quality is still not satisfactory to domestic purposes. Sewage from households nearby
303 is directly discharged into the lake due to the lack of previous urban planning and wastewater
304 treatment plants. It is crucial for the improvement of the water quality of the lakes to treat the
305 sewage and other industrial effluents. Currently, there is only one single sewage treatment
306 plant (Perungudi STP in Fig. 1), which has been adapted to reuse of secondary treated water
307 for construction and other industrial purposes (Manikandan, 2016). The Sembakkam Lake is
308 currently under restoration. Despite the inflows from Selaiyur, Chitlapakkam and
309 Rajakilpakkam with low water quality, it shows a better condition than the upstream lakes.
310 Similar results have been shown by the physio-chemical parameters (Fig. 5). However, it still
311 needs more efforts to become suitable drinking water according to Indian BIS. The high level

312 of phosphate and $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ indicates severe eutrophication (Li et al., 2020). The invasive plant
313 water hyacinth has massively grown in the lake. Water hyacinth has been considered as one of
314 the most productive and worst aquatic plants (Malik, 2007). It grows very fast and results in
315 many negative effects, i.e., destroying the wildlife resources (Penfound and Earle, 1948) and is
316 clogging water bodies (Malik, 2007). In the current restoration project, water hyacinth has been
317 removed from the lake. The project has not been finished yet; further data collection will be
318 necessary to assess the efficiency and achievement of the restoration. Whatsoever, more similar
319 projects should be applied to the other lakes as well.

320 Based on the findings in this study, human activities have huge impact on water quality. Some
321 suggestions can be submitted to the residents, stakeholders, and decision-makers as following:
322 1) The water quality is eutrophic and unsuitable for domestic use. 2) Local authorities should
323 take more preventative measures. For instance, more wastewater treatment plants could be
324 established to process the wastewater before discharging. Besides, proper guidelines could be
325 implied to restrict the concentration of discharged nutrients into the lakes. 3) It would be better
326 to prevent the pollution than to eliminate it afterwards. In this regard, public participation
327 would be important, for instance, proper waste management and raising environmental
328 awareness among the inhabitants of the area would be helpful. For this purpose, the third master
329 plan of Chennai, that will come into force in 2026, is a great opportunity since it includes a
330 long-term vision document produced with a participatory approach. 4) the last but not the least,
331 the land use types which favors the water quality (i.e., grass) could be increased.

332 **5. Conclusion**

333 The measured lake water quality in Pallikaranai catchment is not satisfactory and eutrophic,
334 despite the groundwater surrounding the lakes is used for drinking purpose. In regard of
335 seasonal variation, the lake water quality was better in the rainy/moonson season (Oct.-Dec.)
336 than in the dry season/pre-moonson season (Jul.-Sep.) in 2019. In regard of spatial variation,
337 water quality increases along the flow direction in the cascading system. Human activities, the
338 discharge of domestic, municipal, and industrial effluents combined with the dumping of solid
339 wastes have vital negative impact on water quality in Pallikaranai catchment. The land
340 use/cover types, such as crops, woodland and urban area, show negative impacts and relate to
341 the high level of nutrient concentrations. In opposite, grass land shows positive effects and
342 leads to better water quality. There is the necessity of pollution control and restoration
343 management to ensure the sustainability of the ecosystem. The last but not the least, local
344 authorities should take more preventative measures and public participation in environmental
345 protection should be encouraged to improve the quality of the ecosystem.

346

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